

UNDERSCORING THE RELEVANCE OF WORKLOAD IN ACADEMIC STAFF JOB PERFORMANCE: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCES

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ABSTRACT

Job performance has to do with the behaviour that an individual deliver in order to leverage the value of an organisation over period of time. This study therefore theoretically focused on scoring the relevance of workload in academic staff job performance. The study was based on empirical evidence from other related studies and this forms the basis of the research. Measures of job performance of academic staff as well as concepts of workload and job performance were all discussed extensively. This study also supported and adopted Job Demand-Resources Model (JD-R Model). The Job Demand-Resources Model (JD-R) was proposed by some authors as a model that explores employee well-being. The paper also examined some previous empirical studies that investigated the relationship between the two constructs as basis for underscoring the relevance of workload in job performance. Findings from the reviewed empirical studies generally underscored the seminal role workload plays in the determination of job performance. It was therefore concluded that workload needs to be taken into consideration in the determination of academic staff job performance. The paper therefore recommended that more qualified academic staff should be employed in the system, effective stress management techniques and habit of regular medical checkups should be formed by academic staff.

Keywords: Workload, Job performance, Academic staff

INTRODUCTION

Job performance of academic staff is very germane to the realization of goals and objectives of colleges of education. It determines how effective the colleges are and to a large extent the continuity of the system (Kazimoto, 2016; Razak et al.,

2018; Tentama et al., 2020). Job performance of academic staff (lecturers) is the extent to which they accomplish their designated tasks such as quality teaching, research work and community service with reference to standards set by their college of education. The above

definition shows that there are three ways to measure the job performance of academic staff. They are - quality teaching, research work and community service. (López-Cabarcos et al., 2022).

Employee job performance is the ability and level of results shown by an employee while performing his/her duties or responsibilities at the workplace (Razak et al., 2018). Job performance is a multi-dimensional concept that consists of two aspects: the behavioural (process) aspect and the outcome (result) aspects (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). The behavioural aspect refers to "what people do at work", while the outcome aspect refers to the "results of the individual's behaviour." (Alromaihi et al., 2017) It was emphasized that job performance is the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organisational goals and objectives. (Onalapo et al., 2019). Job performance is regarded as a behaviour that an individual deliver in order to leverage the value of an organisation over period of time (Al-Jedaiaa & Mehre, 2020). Individual job performance is defined as "things that individuals actually do, actions they take, that contribute to the organisation's goals" (Campbell & Wiernik, 2016, p. 4). A scholar defined job performance as the actual

accomplishment of assigned task. It is the actual work done against the expected standard of achievement (Maclean, 2018). It is also viewed as the aggregated financial or non-financial added value by the staff in contribution to the fulfillment both directly and indirectly to the targeted organisational goals (Dajani, 2015)

Job performance is the duties performed by teachers in the school which aimed at achieving both education and school objectives. A scholar defined lecturers' job performance using the outcome dimension, thereby describing it as the extent to which academic staff members achieve educational outcomes expected of them. While this definition is valid, it was not applied in this study because of the difficulties associated with measuring educational outcomes (Onoyase, 2017). It was stated that lecturer performance is the ability of lecturer to perform the assignment in order to complete the job. Performance, in other words, is work presentation, work implementation, work achievement, or work result (Hadiantini et al., 2017). Taking the process dimension adopted in this present study, researchers described academic staff job performance as the degree to which they complete their teaching responsibilities, which include lecture planning, research,

and community service. Although these researchers' approach is used in this present study, they related the process dimensions of lecturers' job performance to motivation but not instructional leadership (Victor & Babatunde, 2014). A similar approach was applied by other researchers but they also related this performance to motivation (Hadiantini et al., 2017).

According to a scholar, lecture planning focuses on using the content outline of the assigned course unit(s) and the learning objectives it seeks to achieve to search for and select relevant subject matter for a particular lecture, segmenting this subject matter into specific content sections and subsections, and determining which subject matter to cover within the allocated time. This scholar continued to show that lesson planning involves determining relevant teaching/learning materials and a pedagogical method to use in order to effectively deliver the subject matter in a manner that cultivates and maintains student attention, interest, and participation necessary to realizing set learning objectives. The scholar was however, descriptive as he did not go beyond explaining what lesson planning involves (McCarthy, 2015)

Lecturers' job performance includes delivering lectures to students as

scheduled by the timetable, and evaluating the students by giving and marking coursework, setting tests and examinations, invigilating and marking them, and submitting their results/marks for final assessment, grading and accrediting (Igbojekwe et al., 2015). This performance further involves supervising research students by creating adequate time for guiding them through their research proposals, projects and dissertations (Ddungu L. 2017). The performance further involves conducting research and publishing findings in reputable academic journals, or using the findings to write textbooks, textbook chapters and articles in media outlets and documentaries (Kakulu, 2016) It further involves lecturers participating in community service by carrying out activities such as public scholarship, participatory research, community partnership, public information networks, and civil literacy scholarship (Ddungu, 2018a)

Despite the crucial role of academic staff performance, the researcher has observed that their job performance in quality teaching, research work and community service in colleges of education, Southwest Nigeria is very poor. Other researchers have also confirmed low job performance amongst academic staff of colleges of education (Tentama et al., 2020; Oguntimehin et al., 2018). This

decline in job performance has therefore made educational stakeholders and researchers to ponder on what could be the factors militating against academic staff job performance in colleges of education as the problem seems to be on the rise.

One very important and critical factor capable of affecting the job performance of academic staff is workload. Workload is the amount of professional and non-professional duties carried out by lecturers in the course of their activities at a particular time (Maclean, 2018). Workload can at times be heavy (overload), normal or light (under load) (Dajani, 1015). Researchers found that work overload will happen when academic staff receive workload beyond their capabilities because of the increase of productivity and performance demand (Malkanathi et al., 2016). Work overload could lead to stress as it places academic staff under time pressure. Stress can produce anxiety that may impair a lecturer's ability to perform a task.

Work under load occurs when lecturers have too little work to do or too little variety in their work. It could result in passivity, low self-esteem, increased frequency of nervous symptoms and complaint, lack of interest in social activity and work

performance output amongst academic staff (Darma & Supriyanto, 2017). Lecturers' burnout, effectiveness and performance could therefore be influenced by having too much or less to do or even having to tackle too difficult work (Hirlak et al., 2018).

Measures of Job Performance of Academic Staff

There are several ways to measure the job performance of academic staff. Academic staff job performance is described as the degree to which they complete their teaching responsibilities (which include lecture planning), research, and community service (Victor & Babatunde, 2014). It therefore means that lecturers' job performance can be measured in terms of lecture planning, research and community service. According to an author, the job performance of academic staff in colleges of education is revealed in their quality teaching, research work and community service (Taiwo, 2014). This is supported by the framework for measuring the lecturers' performance which states that a lecturer's job performance is measured based on his/her research output, quality of teaching, community services among others (Agbionu et al., 2018). Measuring academic staff's performance in institutions of higher learning

implicates an evaluation of teaching and learning, including supervision, research, publication, and community services based on the duties and responsibilities together with other qualities (Muda, 2017).

Concept of Workload

Workload is the number of activities that require expertise and must be done in a certain time in physical and psychological form (Lilin, 2018). Meanwhile, according to authors, workload is the average frequency of each job within a certain period. Furthermore, it is the amount of work that must be borne by an office/organizational unit and is the product of work volume and time norms (Abboh et al., 2019). Definition of workload is a group or a number of activities that must be completed by an organizational unit or position holder within a certain period (Chong et al., 2020). Workload measurement is defined as a technique for obtaining information about the efficiency and effectiveness of the work of an organizational unit, or position holders carried out systematically using job analysis techniques, workload analysis techniques or other management techniques (Chong et al., 2020; Dadich & Olson, 2017).

Based on the several definitions stated above, it can be stated that

workload is the extent to which an individual employee's capacity is needed in completing the tasks assigned to him, which can be indicated from the amount of work that must be done, the time/time constraints owned by the worker in completing his task and views of the individual regarding the work assigned to him (Gunu & Oladepo, 2017). In the school environment, workload is the amount of professional and non-professional duties carried out by the lecturers in the course of their activities at a particular time (Zainal et al., 2015). It is the sum of all activities that take the time of a lecturer. It is also the number of lessons a teacher teaches in a week as per the allocations in the time-table. Workload can be normal, heavy (overload) or light (under load) (Dabara et al., 2020).

Workload is said to be normal if there is a regular balance in the time used to carry out numerous organizational goals and duties in such a way that the mental and physical state of the person doing the work is not affected. When calculating normal workload, three important variables should be considered. These are Task, Time and Frequency of labour. Task refers to the job to be done. Tasks can be broken down into daily, detail and project. Daily tasks are those routine jobs that need to be carried out on a

daily basis, an example of such tasks for a lecturer is teaching. Detail tasks can be performed on a set-schedule basis and is more involved than daily work. Examples of detail tasks are supervision of student projects, marking and grading of scripts and research and publications. Project tasks are performed less frequently: anywhere from weekly to annually. Examples of these are community service and attending meetings that are school related. Time is the amount of hours allocated for each tasks. Time here can be divided into teaching contact hours, attributed hours for teaching preparation, attributed hours for evaluation and attributed hours for functions. Teaching contact hours represents hours spent in the classroom instructing students. This is a scheduled teaching hour assigned to the teacher by the university. Attributed hours of preparation represent the number of hours spent preparing for classroom activities. This is based on how a lecturer prepares his lecture notes, how many levels the lecturer is teaching at once and how many times the lecturer has taught the course in the past because the more experienced a lecturer is at delivering a specific course, the fewer hours he will spend on preparation. Attributed hours of evaluation have to do with the number of hours spent evaluating and grading student's

assignments, projects, teaching practice, examinations etcetera. Attributed hours for complimentary functions represent the number of hours assigned for routine out of class assistance to students, community service, research and publication and normal administrative duties (Amini-Philips & Okonmah, 2020).

Workload is heavy when lecturers feel they are being asked to do more than time or ability permits (Dabara et al., 2020). Roles overload are the inability of staff to complete their tasks because of too high yield standards, and completion of tasks with inadequate provision of time (Sajjad, 2016). Researchers found that work overload will happen when staff receive workload beyond their capabilities because of the increase of productivity and performance demand (Usono & Etuk, 2016). Role overload also occurs when an employee has many tasks to be completed under limited time and pressure so that it does not match the ability of the employee to complete the task. When the work becomes too much, it would cause physical and mental fatigue, even saturation and stress and burnout (Sajjad, 2016). Work under load occurs when lecturers have too little work to do or too little variety in their work (Osaat & Ekechukwu, 2017).

Concept of Job Performance

Employee job performance is the ability and level of results shown by an employee while performing his/her duties or responsibilities at the workplace (Razak et al., 2018). Job performance is a multi-dimensional concept that consists of two aspects: the behavioural (process) aspect and the outcome (result) aspects (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). The behavioural aspect refers to "what people do at work", while the outcome aspect refers to the "results of the individual's behaviour" (Alromaihi et al., 2017). It was emphasized that job performance is the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organisational goals and objectives (Onalapo et al., 2019).

It was also rightly put that performance can be regarded as any behaviour directed toward the task or goal accomplishment (Oguntimehin et al., 2018). Job performance generally refers to whether a person performs the job well. It is the output record of a specific job function or activity at a particular time. It is the result of specific functions or activities of workers in a given period of time¹³. Performance in a job is strictly a behaviour and a separate entity from the outcomes of a particular job which relate to success

and productivity (Alsuwailem & Elnaga, 2016). It is the extent to which each personnel executes the expected roles with reference to identified standards set by the organisation (Oguntimehin et al., 2018).

Job performance is regarded as a behaviour that an individual deliver in order to leverage the value of an organisation over period of time (Al-Jedaiaa Y. & Mehrez A. 2020). Individual job performance is defined as "things that individuals actually do, actions they take, that contribute to the organisation's goals" (Campbell & Wiernik, 2016). A scholar defined job performance as the actual accomplishment of assigned task. It is the actual work done against the expected standard of achievement (Maclean I. F. 2018). It is also viewed as the aggregated financial or non-financial added value by the staff in contribution to the fulfillment both directly and indirectly to the targeted organisational goals (Dajani, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

This study is supported by the following Job Demand-Resources Model (JD-R Model). The Job Demand-Resources Model (JD-R) proposed by some authors is a model that explores employee well-being. It is used by managers to predict employee engagement and employee

burnout (Salim, 2020) The model categorises working conditions into two groups which are: work indices (demand) and job resources/positives. The model essentially states that when work indices (demand) are high and job resources are low, then factors such as stress and burnout are increased. Alternatively, when work indices are high and job resources are high, then factors such as work engagement and performance levels are improved (Khudhair, 2020). According to the model, job characteristics of different occupations such as the teaching profession may be classified either as work indices (demand) or job resources.

On one hand, work indices are those aspects of a work (physical, psychological, social, and organizational) that require sustained physical and/or psychological (cognitive and emotional) effort from the employee and are therefore associated with certain psychological and/or physiological costs. Examples include: workload, role conflict and role ambiguity. On the other hand, job resources are those aspects of a job (physical, psychological, social, and organizational) that are functional in achieving work goals, reducing work indices and the associated costs (psychological and/or physiological), or promoting personal growth,

learning, and development. Examples include: management support, quality relationships and adequate facilities (Salim, 2020, Khudhair et al., 2020).

In line with this JD-R model, high work indices may reduce wellbeing and performance due to the depletion of personal resources (such as time, physical and emotional energy) (Salim, 2020). If an individual (lecturer) has few resources available at the end of the day due to energy depletion at work, he or she will be less likely to be involved with his work, which may give rise to reduced performance. Furthermore, the buffer hypothesis of the model claims that high job resources (such as job aids, management support) may offset the harmful impact of work indices on job performance (Salim, 2020; Khudhair et al., 2020). Accordingly, specific job designs in which lecturers are burdened with high work indices, but lack adequate levels of job resources, are particularly likely to decrease job performance (Salim, 2020).

Workload and Job Performance: Some Empirical Evidences

There have been some empirical evidences that underscore the importance of workload in the determination of job performance. For instance, some researchers investigated academic staff workload

and job performance in higher institutions in Delta State. Six research questions were answered and six corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of allowance. The research adopted the correlational research design. The population of the research comprised 164 Heads of Department (HODs) in six public and private higher institutions in Delta State. A sample of 115 HODs were drawn through stratified random sampling technique and employed for the research. Two instruments titled “Academic staff Workload Scale” and ‘Academic Staff Job Performance Scale” were employed for data collection. Face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were determined using Cronbach’s Alpha reliability estimate and the reliability coefficient of the questionnaires were .989 and .873 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed to answer research questions. The finding shows that there is significant high negative relationship between academic staff teaching workload and their job performance. As the scores of academic staff teaching workload was increasing, the scores of job performance was decreasing.

This result is not surprising, the implication is that, much involvement

of academic staff in instructional delivery affects their daily performance negatively and as such there is need for allocation of assistant academic staff to academic staff in teaching in order to reduce their workload and enhance instructional delivery. The results of the research also showed that, there is significant high negative relationship between academic staff supervision of students’ project workload and their productivity. This implies that, as the scores of academic staff supervision of students’ project workload was increasing the scores of productivity were decreasing. The result of this research is not surprising. It implies that, academic staff supervision of students’ project decreases their performance in their daily service. This means that, as the scores of academic staff research workload was increasing, the scores of productivity was decreasing. The finding also implies that, when academic staff engage in much research, it affects their job performance negatively. The difference could be the sample size and areas the studies were carried out. The finding of the research also showed that, there is a significant high negative relationship between academic staff participation in community service workload and their productivity in higher institutions in Delta State.

A scholar revealed that too much workload on teaching and duties was not conducive for academic staff teaching performance (Saridakis et al., 2018). Scholars also found that workload related stress significantly influence the job effectiveness of academic staff in terms of publications, community service and teaching effectiveness (Velmurugan, 2016). Academic staff burnout and performance could therefore be influenced by having too much or less to do or even having to tackle too difficult work. A scholar agree that staff are usually conditioned to work long hours in a very competitive environment like a higher institution setting with little or no rest or sleep which may likely cause high rate of stress and affect the quality of work performance.

Researchers noted that in this era of downsizing which has left organizations including colleges of education with relatively small workforce (academic staff) compared to the volume of available work in the organizations, a significant proportion of staff have difficulty performing their primary assignment at work and family or social obligations due to work Indices usually results in stressful situations. In many occasions, work that would normally be for three or more people is left for one person to do because

educational institution heads do not want to carry heavy wage bill. The consequences are usually work overload and long hours at work by staff. The scholars showed that long hours inherent in job stress do not allow staff in Nigerian tertiary institutions to perform at their optimal level of productivity and efficiency. Long hours of work when it is not moderated causes severe stress that breaks academic staff down and lower their performance. If it is allowed to persist in an organizational climate may become hazardous to staff, affect their health and performance. Long hours of work affect worker performance negatively. The government and policy makers should strive to create a working environment where there is stress-free climate by reducing the long hours of work and other stress causing agents (Atah, 2019).

A similar research was done on the influence of workload toward work performance. The research was conducted using a survey method with a path analysis testing hypothesis. 90 principals in Police Women Educational institution-Polri were chosen as samples which were selected using simple random sampling technique. The results of the research revealed a direct negative influence of workload toward work performance of principals (Etor,

2014). A research work sought to identify the effects of heavy workload on performance of academic staff of different ranks at tertiary education level. A cross-sectional research was conducted with the help of a questionnaire in three public sector Higher institutions of District, Jamshoro. A sample of 300 participants of male and female academic staff were selected for the research as the teaching profession ranks on the top of stressful jobs. Results revealed that conflict, heavy workload, lack of information about job description, lack of job independence and lack of motivation are unenthusiastically associated with all job satisfaction aspects. The teaching staff who have high level of workload stress possess low level job satisfaction and performance (El Rahman, 2017).

A research examined the perceived influence of work overload on academic staff job performance in higher institutions in Rivers State. The research was guided by three research objectives from which three research questions were posed and three hypotheses formulated. The research adopted a descriptive survey research design with a population of 337 academic staff (189 males and 148 females) from the Faculties of Education in the three public higher institutions in Rivers State (Higher

institution of Port Harcourt, Rivers State Higher institution and Ignatius Ajuru Higher institution of Education). The entire population was employed for the research; hence the census sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Influence of Work Overload on Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire". The instrument was validated by experts in the Departments of Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation. Reliability values were .893 and .879 for both questionnaires respectively. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of allowance. Results revealed among others that teaching of many courses in a semester, supervision of large number of undergraduate projects and post-graduate theses/dissertations negatively influence job performance of academic staff in higher institutions in Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the Federal and State Governments should employ more academic staff either as contract, adjunct, sabbatical or permanent staff so as to reduce the workload of the academic staff and improve on their performance (Conant, 2017).

CONCLUSION

The conclusion that can be drawn from the review of some previous empirical studies in the paper is that workload needs to be taken into consideration in the determination of academic staff job performance. In other words, we need to ensure that for a better performance of academic staff, their workloads should be moderate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above conclusion, it is therefore recommended that:

1. More qualified academic staff should be employed in the system with a view to reducing the workloads of the staff. This is to ensure improved job performance among the academic staff.
2. Effective stress management techniques should always be adopted by academic staff for them to keep healthy and perform optimally.
3. Habit of regular medical check ups should also be formed by the academic staff. This will enable them to know their health status.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, N. H., Mustapha, A., Wahab, E., Ahmad, M. K. & Rahim, R. A. (2020). Does academics' workload affect research performance? *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(2), 5840-5845.
- Adekanye, E.A. & Nduka, S.C. (2017). Work-family conflict, job satisfaction and job performance of female librarians in nine selected federal academic libraries in South-West, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 10(2) 216-227.
- Adiguzel, Z. (2019). Examining of the effects of employees on work stress, role conflict and job insecurity on organizational culture. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 1(4), 37-48.
- Agbionu., U. C., Anyalor, M., & Nwali, A. C. (2018). Employee engagement and performance of lecturers in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *Journal of Education & Entrepreneurship Formerly Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 5(2), 69-87. <https://doi.org/10.26762/jee.2018.40000015>.
- Ahmada, J., Saffardin, S. F., & Teoh, K. B. (2020). How Does Job Demands and Job Resources affect work engagement towards burnout? The Case of Penang Preschool.

- International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 12(5), 283-293.
- Alam., S., Haerani, S., Amar, M.Y., & Sudirman, I. (2015). Role conflict and role ambiguity in higher education. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 4(1), 1-7.
- Al-Jedaiaa, Y., & Mehrez, A. (2020). The effect of performance appraisal on job performance in governmental sector: The mediating role of motivation. *Management Science Letters*, 10, 2077–2088. Doi: 10.5267/j.msl.2020.2.003.
- Alrawahi, S., Sellgren, S. F., Alwahaibi, N., Altouby, S., & Brommels, M. (2019). Factors affecting job satisfaction among medical laboratory technologists in University Hospital Oman: An exploratory study. *The International journal of health planning and management*. 34(1), 763- 775
- Alromaihi., M.A., Alshomaly, Z.A., & George, S. (2017). Job satisfaction and employee performance: A theoretical review of the relationship between the two variables. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 1-20.
- Alsuwailem, A., & Elnaga., A. A. (2016). Exploring the relationship between personality and job performance "new approach". *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(12), 43-53.
- Ariffin, H.D.F, (2015). Workload, role conflict and work-life balance among employees of an enforcement agency in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business, Economic and Law*, 8(2), 32- 57.
- Ariffin., H.D.F., Sahaib, N.S.M., & Mazhisham, P.H. (2017). The influence of role ambiguity, role conflict, work overload, and relationship conflict on job performance. *Proceeding of 2nd International Conference on Law, Economics and Education (ICONLEE)*. Grand Bluewave Hotel Shah Alam, Malaysia.
- Atanda, A. I., & Olasupo, I. O. (2018). A survey of academic staff research output in the university of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. *East African Journal of Educational Research and Policy*, 13(1), 79-94.

- Bruggen, A. (2015). An empirical investigation of the relationship between workload and performance. *Management Decision*, 53(10), 2377-2389.
- Dajani, M.A.Z. (2015). The impact of employee engagement on job performance and organisational commitment in the Egyptian banking sector. *Journal of Business Management and Sciences*, 3(5), 138-147.
- Malkanthi, S.P.S., & Ali, M.A.M.H. (2016). *Impact of job design on employees' performance in people's banks of Ampara district*. 5th Annual International Research Conference.
- Darma, P.S., & Supriyanto, A.S. (2017). The effect of compensation on satisfaction and employee performance. *Management and Economics Journal*, 1(1), 69-78.
- Ddungu, L. (2018a). Evaluation as a predictor of academic staff participation in community service in universities in Uganda. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 8(2), 3-19.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A.B., & Xanthopoulou, D. (2019). Job demands-resources theory and the role of individual cognitive and behavioral strategies. In T. Taris, M. Peeters, & H. De Witte (Eds.), *The fun and frustration of modern working life: Contributions from an occupational health psychology perspective* (pp. 94–104). Pelckmans Pro.
- Ekechukwu, R.O., & Isiguzo, B.C. (2016). Stress and its associated health problems among nonacademic staff in Nigerian universities: A case study of university of Port Harcourt. *European Journal of Psychological Research*, 3(1), 16-27.
- El Rahman, R.M.A. (2017). The relationship between workplace incivility and nurses job satisfaction on intent to leave. *Academia. edu*.
- Fonkeng, C. (2018). *Effects of job-stress on employee performance in an enterprise: A microfinance institution in Cameroon*. Thesis submitted to Centria University of Applied Sciences.
- Foong, L., Mogana, P., & Loh, C. (2018). Private sector early child care and education in Malaysia: Workforce readiness for further education. *Kajian Malaysia*, 36(1), 127–154.

- Gerich, J. & Weber, C. (2020). The Ambivalent Appraisal of Job Demands and the Moderating Role of Job Control and Social support for burnout and job satisfaction. *Social Indicators Research*, 14(8), 251-280.
Doi.org/10.1007/s11205-019-02195-9
- Hadiantini., R., Pandia, S. P., & Kaburuan, E.R. (2017). Lecturer performance factors in private universities in Bandung City. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*,7(4),231-239.
DOI:10.5296/ijhrs.v7i4.12079
- Hardiani., W.A.A., Rahardja, E. & Yuniawan, A. (2017). Effect of role conflict and role overload to burnout and its impact on cyberloafing. *Jurnal Bisnis STRATEGI*, 26(2), 89-99.
- Harmen., H., Amanah, D., Harahap, D. A., & Naibaho, F. (2019). Sources of job stress dimension effect on employee performance. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(9), 581–590
<https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM.2019.v02i09.016>
- Hassel, S., & Ridout, N. (2018). An investigation of first-year students' and lecturers' expectations of university education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(1), 2218-2233.
- Hirlak., B., Ciftci, G. E., & Balikci, O. (2018). The effects of organisational climate on the employee performance: The mediating role of employees' creativity. *Monographs and Studies of the Jagiellonian University Institute of Public Affairs*, 81- 91.
- Hosain, M.S. (2016). Teaching Workload and Performance: An Empirical Analysis on Some Selected Private Universities of Bangladesh. *International Journal of English and Education*, 5(3) 1-12.
- Igbojekwe, P.A., Ugo-Okoro, C.P., & Agbonye, C.O. (2015). Performance evaluation of academic staff in universities and colleges in Nigeria: The missing criteria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(3), 627- 640.
- Jalal, R. N. U. D., & Zaheer, M. A. (2017). Does job satisfaction mediate the relationship of workload, remuneration and psychological reward with job performance? *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(9), 64–79.

- Janib, J., Rasdi, R. M., Omar, Z., Alias, S.N., Zaremohzzabieh, Z., & Ahrari, S. (2021). The Relationship between Workload and Performance of Research University Academics in Malaysia: The Mediating Effects of Career Commitment and Job Satisfaction. *Asian Journal of University Education (AJUE)*, 17(2), 85-99
- Jayaweera, T. (2015). Impact of work environmental factors on job performance, mediating role of work motivation: a study of hotel sector in England. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 10(3), 271- 278.
- Jimoh., A.M. Ukpabi, I.D. & Salaudeen, K..K. (2021) Job satisfaction and personality characteristics as correlates of lecturers' performance in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Global Scientific Journal*. 9(7) 269-283
- Kazimoto, P. (2016). Employee engagement and organisational performance of retails enterprises". *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 6, 516-525
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2016.64047>
- Lashkariani, S. O., & Motevalli, S. (2020). The influence of job stress on job satisfaction among female lecturers. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(4), 1263-1268.
- Latip., H.A. Tak., A. H. Rahaman, M. M. & Abdul Kohar, U. H. (2018). Managing work-life family demands towards job satisfaction among family business entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(14), 187–199.
- López-Cabarcos., M. Á., Vázquez-Rodríguez, P., & Quiñoá-Piñeiro, L. M. (2022). An approach to employees' job performance through work environmental variables and leadership behaviours. *Journal of Business Research*, 140, 361-369
- Lynch, M. & Wright, D. (2019). A Descriptive Correlational Investigation into Factors that Impact on Job Satisfaction among 40 Conveniently Selected Participants in an Urban Setting. *Social Science Journal*. 3, 403-413
- Maclean, I. F. (2018) In-service training and teachers' job performance in public senior

- secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11(3B) 493-520
- Manaf, A., Matin, M. & Zulaikha, S. (2019). Effect of Work Environment and Work Loads on the Performance of Police Educators in Sepolwan Lemdiklat Polri. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Studies*, 1(5) 461-466.
- Mohammed, A. & Wang, J. (2018). Impact of Laissez-Faire Leadership on Role Ambiguity and Role Conflict: Implications for Job Performance. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development*, 4(1), 29-43.
- Muda., H., Ali, M. H. & Jusoh, M. (2017). Measuring teaching and learning performance in higher education. *International Journal of Education, Psychology and Counselling*, 2(6), 57-70.
- Mujiyanto, Sugiharto, D.W.P., Pramono, S.E. & Sudana, M. (2020). Influence of reward, leadership, and organisational culture to lecturer performance of Indonesia Buddhis Religious College. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. 7(7), 449-455.
- Odor, H.O. (2019). Work related stress and employee commitment at Delta State Polytechnic, Oguashi Ukwu, Delta State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Resources, Administration and Management*. 19(1), 25-36.
- Oguntimehin., Y. A., Kuewumi, O. A., & Adeyemi, M. (2018). Assessment of influence of quality assurance indices on secondary school's teachers' job performance. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy (BJSEP)*, 12(1) 123-138
- Ojukwu, H.S., & Nwankwo, C.N. (2021). Effect of job-related stress on lecturers' performance in Nigeria's federal universities in Southeast region. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*. 4(1) 87-109.
- Onaolapo., A. A., Olajiga, G. D., & Onaolapo, M.T. (2019). Teachers job performance in secondary schools, Nigeria: the effect of family satisfaction and job satisfaction. *The International Journal of Business &*

- Management*. 7(3) 65-69 DOI: 10.24940/theijbm/2019/v7/i3/BM1903-011.
- Onoyase, A. (2017). Motivation and job performance of lecturers of tertiary institutions in nigeria: implication for counseling. *World Journal of Educational Research*. 4(2), 280-289.
- Opunne, T.A. & Fekarurhobo, B.E. (2021) Perceived Influence of Work Overload on Academic Staff Job Performance in Universities in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 9(2) 56-67.
- Osaat, D. S. & Ekechukwu, R. (2017). Managing Workload of Academic Staff for Job Effectiveness in Nigerian Universities: A Study of University of Port Harcourt in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE)*. 4(12), 102-108. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0412013>
- Palomino M.N. & Frezatti, F. (2016). Role conflict, role ambiguity and job satisfaction: Perceptions of the Brazilian controllers. *Revista de Administração [RAUSP]*. 51(2) 165-181
Doi:10.5700/rausp1232
- Poulsen., M.G., Khan., A., Poulsen., E.E., Khan, S.R. & Poulsen, A.A. (2016). Work engagement in cancer care: The power of co-worker and supervisor support. *European Journal of Oncology Nursing*. 21, 134-138.
- Pourteimour, S. Yaghmaei, S. & Babamohamadi, H. (2021). The relationship between mental workload and job performance among Iranian nurses providing care to COVID-19 patients: A cross-sectional study. *J Nurs Manag.* 21,1723–1732. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13305>
- Razak., A., Sarpan, S., & Ramlan, R. (2018). Influence of promotion and job satisfaction on employee performance. *Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance Research*, 3(1), 18-27. DOI: 10.20448/2002.31.18.27. ISSN: 2521-3830
- Saleem., M.I., Malik, M., & Qureshi, S.S. (2021). Work stress hampering employee performance during COVID-19: Is Safety Culture Needed? *Frontial Psychology*, 12(6),1-13.

- DOI:10.3389/fpsyg.2021.655839
- Setiawan., A. Hasibuan., H.A. Siahaan., A.P.U., Indrawan., M.I. Rusiadi., I. F. Wakhyuni., E. Astuti., D. Novalina, A. & Rahayu, S. (2018). Dimensions of Cultural Intelligence and Technology Skills on Employee Performance. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(10), 50-60.
- Shafi, M. & Memon, A.S. (2015). Effects of heavy workload on performance of teaching staff. A Cross-sectional Study of University Teachers. *Researcher*. 7(6) 30-33
- Silaban, R.L., Handaru, A. W. & Saptono, A. (2021). Effect of Workload, Competency, and Career Development on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment Intervening Variables. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World*. 3(01), 294–311 Retrieved from <https://www.growingscholar.org/journal/index.php/TIJOSS/W/article/view/126>
- Sofoluwe., A. O., Akinsolu, A. O., & Ogbudinkpa, I. C. (2015). The relationship between gender, stress and job performance among academic staff in tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*. 11(34), 522-535.
- Subon, F. & Sigie, M. M. (2016). Burnout among Primary and Secondary School Teachers in Samarahan District. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*. 21(8), 28–41
- Suryaman, (2018). Indonesian private university lecturer performance improvement model to improve a sustainable organisation performance. *International Journal of Higher Education*. 7(1), 59-68
doi:10.5430/ijhe.v7n1p59
- Tancinco, N. P. (2016). Status of Teachers' Workload and Performance in State Universities of Eastern Visayas: Implications to Educational Management. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 18(6) 46-57.
- Teng., M. Hassan., Z. Kasa., M. Nor, N. N. M. Bandar, N. F. A. & Ahmad, R. (2020). Mediating role of Boredom in the Workplace on Turnover Intention: A Proposed Framework. *International Journal of Academic Research in*

- Business and Social Sciences*. 10(12) 924–938.
- Tentama, F., Rahmawati, P. A. & Muhopilah, P. (2019). The effect and implications of work stress and workload on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. 8(11) 2498-2502.
- Tentama., F. Dewi, L. & Meilani, E.R. (2020). The role of work discipline and autonomy on employee performance: A case of private university in Indonesia. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(1) 4152-4157.
- Thammarak, S. & Witthaya, M. (2020). The Influence of Workload and Co – Worker Attitude on Job Satisfaction among Employees of Pharmaceutical Industry in Bangkok, Thailand: The Mediating Role of Training. *Sys Rev Pharm*. 11(2) 603-611
- Usoro, A.A. & Etuk, G.R. (2016). Work Related Stress and Job Effectiveness of University Lectures in Cross River and Akwalbom States, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*. 3(1), 34-41
- Wen., B., Zhou, Z., Hu, Y. & Zhang, X. (2020). Role stress and turnover intention of front-line hotel employees: The roles of burnout and service climate. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 11(36) 1-13
doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00036
- Yang, T., Shen, Y.M., Zhu, M., Liu, Y., Deng, J., Chen, Q. & See, L.C. (2016). Effects of co-worker and supervisor support on job stress and presenteeism in an aging workforce: a structural equation modelling approach. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 13(72) 1-15
- Yousefi, M. & Abdullah, A.G.K. (2019). The Impact of Organizational Stressors on Job Performance among Academic Staff. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(3), 561-576.
<https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.12334a>
- Zaki, H. & Marzolina, S. (2018). The Effect of Workload and Compensation on Turnover Intention through Job Satisfaction in Employees of PT. Adira Quantum Multifinance Pekanbaru Branch. *Journal of Boxing*

Business Management. 8(3)
108-117
Zamanian, Z., Sarvestani, M. R.,
Sedaghati, M., Ghatmiri, M. &
Kouhnavard, B. (2016).
Assessment of the Relation

between Subjective Workload
and Job Satisfaction in
University Faculty and Staff.
Journal of Ergonomics. 3(4),
1–10